

First record of the genus *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956 from the Eastern Atlantic (Gastropoda: Rissoidae), with the description of a new species

Primera cita del género *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956 para el Atlántico Oriental (Gastropoda: Rissoidae), con la descripción de una nueva especie

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956 currently only includes species from the Indo-Pacific. A new eastern Atlantic species of this genus is here described from Boa Vista Island, Cape Verde Archipelago on the basis of two empty shells. This is the first record of a *Parashiela* species outside the Indo-Pacific. The new taxon is compared with the most similar congeneric species.

RESUMEN

El género *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956 actualmente incluye sólo especies del Indo-Pacífico. Se describe una nueva especie de este género del Atlántico oriental, procedente de la isla de Boa Vista, archipiélago de Cabo Verde, basándose en dos conchas vacías. Esta es la primera cita de una especie de *Parashiela* fuera del Indo-Pacífico. El nuevo taxón se compara con las especies congénicas más similares.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Caenogastropoda, East Atlantic, *Parashiela*, new species, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Caenogastropoda, Atlántico este, *Parashiela*, nuevas especies, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956 (Rissooidea, Rissoidae) includes species of a small size for the family, less than 2

mm in length, nonumbilicate or with a narrow umbilical fissure, an aperture with duplicate peristome, almost circu-

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lar, slightly angled or lacking anterior or posterior angulations, outer lip orthocone or prosocline, with varix; axial ribs extending to the base, a fine spiral microsculpture densely and minutely granulated, no spiral cords or one to four strong spiral cords on the body whorl, and one or two cords on first whorls. The protoconch is smooth except for one or two weak spiral threads when multispiral, or with irregular spiral ridges when paucispiral (AMATI, DI GIULIO & OLIVERIO, 2023: 834). Head-foot: cephalic tentacles rather short, ciliated, with parallel sides; a short posterior pallial tentacle and a short, narrow metapodial tentacle; long, distinct anterior pedal gland, no posterior pedal gland. Operculum: oval, thin, nucleus eccentric (after PONDER 1985: 59). No fossil specimens of *Parashiela* have been reported so far.

Eight extant species have been described and named from the Indo-West Pacific (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023); however, the actual number of species is certainly higher (VAN GEMERT, 2016: 8), with several additional species recently recognized, but as yet unnamed (AMATI *ET AL.*, 2023: 838, table 4; Fig. 3). One of these still unnamed species (AMATI *ET AL.*, 2023: 842) is here described on the basis of two shells from the Cape Verde Islands and represents the only known record of the genus for the Atlantic Ocean. Otherwise, the family Rissoidae is represented in the Cape Verde Archipelago by species of the genera *Rissoa* Desmarest, 1814, *Alvania* Risso, 1826, *Botryphallus* Ponder, 1990, *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917, *Manzonia* Brusina, 1870, *Obtusella* Cossmann, 1921 and *Plagyostila* de Folin, 1872 (e.g.: ROLÁN, 1987; 2005; MOOLENBEEK & ROLÁN, 1988; ROLÁN *ET AL.*, 1993).

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
 Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960
 Order LITTORINIMORPHA Golikov & Starobogatov, 1975
 Superfamily RISSOIDEA Gray, 1847
 Family RISSOIDAE Gray, 1847

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We examined two empty shells retrieved from a sample of bioclastic sand from the type locality. The specimens were studied and measured under a Kyowa stereomicroscope, with a micrometric eyepiece (with magnification $\times 90$, $\pm 10\%$ deviation), using the method of VERDUIN (1982) for counting whorls. Photographs have been taken with a Sony Cyber-shot DSC-W110 digital camera mounted on a Kyowa KBS and a Kyowa SDZ-P stereomicroscopes; image stacking was performed with the software Combine-Z (HADLEY 2006). SEM photographs were taken with a FE-SEM ZEISS Sigma Gemini 300 at the Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy (LIME: "Roma Tre" University, Roma). We have used a standardised format for the citation of specimen data in the "Type material", as described by CHESTER *ET AL.* (2019), with the following data-fields: Country (or major geographic area) • number of specimens (lv and/or dd); locality data (from largest to smallest); geographic coordinates (in decimal degrees); other collecting data; collection and catalogue code.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CS-PM: Private collection of Carlo Smriglio and Paolo Mariottini, Roma (Italy).
 dd: empty shell(s).
 LIME: Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, Dipartimento di Scienze, "Roma Tre" University, Rome (Italy).
 MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (France).
 SEM: scanning electron microscope.

Figure 1. *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp. A-C: holotype, Cape Verde, Boa Vista Island, Baía da Teodora, height 1.27 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-28637); D-F: paratype, Cape Verde, Boa Vista Island, Baía da Teodora, height 1.07 mm (coll. CS-PM).

Figura 1. *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, Cabo Verde, Isla Boa Vista, Baía da Teodora, altura 1,27 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-28637); D-F: paratipo, Cabo Verde, Isla Boa Vista, Baía da Teodora, altura 1,07 mm (col. CS-PM).

Genus *Parashiela* Laseron, 1956

Type species. — *Parashiela ambulata* Laseron, 1956: 439, 479, fig. 145 (type by original designation).

Parashiela caboverdensis n. sp. (Figs. 1, 2)

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Type material: CAPE VERDE ISLANDS. *Holotype* • 1 dd (height 1.32 mm, width 0.82 mm, Figs. 1A–C; 2A–C); Boa Vista I., Baía da Teodora; 16.1917, -22.9167; beached; MNHN-IM-2000-28637. *Paratype* • 1 dd (height 1.07 mm, width 0.72 mm, Figs. 1D–F; 2D); same data as holotype; coll. CS-PM.

Type locality: Cape Verde, Boa Vista Island, Baía da Teodora, 16.1917, -22.9167.

Etymology: The specific name is after the area of the type locality (Cape Verde Archipelago).

Figure 2. *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp., SEM micrographs. A–C: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-28637), Cape Verde, Boa Vista Island, Baía da Teodora, height 1.27 mm. (A) shell, (B) detail of the protoconch microsculpture, (C) detail of the teleoconch microsculpture. D: paratype (coll. CS-PM), same locality, height 1.07 mm, shell in dorsal view.

Figura 2. *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp., micrografías electrónicas de barrido. A–C: holotipo (MNHN-IM-2000-28637), Cabo Verde, isla Boa Vista, Baía da Teodora, altura 1,27 mm. (A) concha, (B) detalle de la microescultura de la protoconcha, (C) detalle de la microescultura de la teleoconcha. D: paratipo (col. CS-PM), misma localidad, altura 1,07 mm, concha en vista dorsal.

Diagnosis: *Parashiela* of medium size for the genus, height <1.30 mm, ovate-conic. Protoconch multispiral with two thin spiral threads. Teleoconch with one strong, spirally cord, and strong axial ribs extending to the base. Microsculpture of spirally arranged microgranules. Peristome duplicated, almost circular, outer lip orthocline, slightly sinuous, internally smooth. Umbilical fissure very narrow. Coloration white.

Description of the holotype: Shell (Figs. 1A–C; 2A–C) of medium size for the genus, height 1.27 mm, width 0.82 mm, height/width ratio 1.55, rather robust, ovate-conical.

Protoconch (Fig. 2B) multispiral, low, of 1.8 whorls, height 0.278 mm, nucleus diameter 0.044 mm, first half whorl diameter 0.122 mm, maximum diameter 0.278 mm; protoconch I smooth, protoconch II almost smooth,

Table I. Measurements of shells of *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp., in mm, with mean values.
 Tabla I. Medidas de las conchas de *Parashiela caboverdensis* n. sp., en mm, con valores medios.

	holotype	paratype	mean
Shell height	1.27	1.07	1.17
Shell width	0.82	0.72	0.77
Shell height/Width ratio	1.55	1.49	1.52
Aperture height	0.53	0.48	0.51
Shell height/aperture height ratio	2.40	2.23	2.32
N° of whorls	2.75	2.25	2.50
N° axial ribs on last whorls	15	11	13
N° spiral cordlets on first whorls	1	1	1

Protoconch	holotype	paratype	mean
Height	0.278	0.240	0.259
Diameter of nucleus	0.044	0.044	0.044
Diameter of first half whorl	0.122	0.122	0.122
Maximum diameter	0.278	0.278	0.278
N° of whorls	1.8	1.8	1.8
Multispiral	yes	yes	yes

with two thin spiral threads on the lower third (Fig. 2B). Protoconch I–II boundary weak, sinuous. Protoconch-teleoconch boundary marked, with sinusigera notch (Fig. 2B).

Teleoconch of 2.75 convex whorls. Axial sculpture on the last whorl of 15 strong prosocline ribs, reaching the base and entering the very narrow umbilical fissure; interspaces three to four times as wide as ribs. Spiral sculpture of one strong cordlet, on the adapical quarter of the whorls. Small rounded tubercles at the intersections. Microsculpture of dense spiral threads, made of fused microgranules (Fig. 2C). Umbilical fissure very narrow. Aperture ovate-piriform, height 0.53 mm, height/aperture height ratio 2.40, peristome duplicate; outer lip orthocline, slightly sinuous, expanded and strongly thickened, with numerous growth striae; columellar lip angled medially.

Colour uniform white.

Operculum and soft parts unknown.

Distribution: The species is known only from the type locality.

Variability: Only two specimens examined, both adults: no significant varia-

tion detected. Minimum adult height 1.07 mm (paratype), maximum 1.27 mm (holotype) (see Table I).

Remarks: The holotype has a foraminiferal test stuck in the aperture.

Parashiela ambulata Laseron, 1956, from the Indo-West Pacific (LASERON, 1956: 439, fig. 145; PONDER, 1985: 50, 153, figs. A–E; AMATI ET AL., 2023: 837, figs. 24A–C, 25A–G, 26A–L), has a very similar outline, but differs from *P. caboverdensis* n. sp., in having the spiral cord placed almost medially on the teleoconch whorls *vs* on the adapical quarter, and in the protoconch with a single spiral thread in the lower third *vs* two well-spaced threads in the lower half.

Parashiela invisibilis (Hedley, 1899), from the Pacific Ocean (HEDLEY, 1899: 418, fig. 9; AMATI ET AL., 2023: 836, figs. 22A–C), differs from *P. caboverdensis* n. sp. in its two teleoconch spiral cords *vs* one.

Parashiela liddelliana (Hedley, 1907), from the Pacific Ocean (HEDLEY, 1907: 494, pl. xvii, fig. 24; AMATI ET AL., 2023: 837, figs. 23A–C), differs from *P. caboverdensis* n. sp. in the lack of teleoconch spiral cords, and the thinner and more numerous axial ribs (20 *vs* 11–15).

Figure 3. Localities of collection of *Parashiela*. Blue dots: checked literature records (after AMATI ET AL., 2023: 838, table 4); red dot, *P. caboverdensis* n. sp.

Figura 3. Localidades de recolección de *Parashiela*. Puntos azules: registros bibliográficos verificados (según AMATI ET AL., 2023: 838, tabla 4); punto rojo, *P. caboverdensis* n. sp.

Parashiela soniae Amati, Di Giulio and Oliverio, 2023, from the Pacific Ocean (AMATI ET AL., 2023: 850, figs. 32A–H, 33A–E), differs from *P. caboverdensis* n. sp. in the lack of teleoconch spiral cords, the suture less undulated, the different microsculpture of the teleoconch (dense microgranules vaguely arranged in spiral series vs dense threads, made of fused microgranules in *P. caboverdensis* n. sp.), and the paucispiral vs multispiral protoconch.

The genus *Parashiela* was not recorded in the Atlantic, and particularly, from Cape Verde (ROLÁN ET AL., 1993; ROLÁN,

2005), prior to our record (Fig. 3). We have excluded any instance of contamination with Indo-Pacific samples, but this record (admittedly based on only two empty shells) remains rather odd. It is remarkable that on the one side, the vast majority of species of *Parashiela* (AMATI ET AL., 2023: table 4) have protoconch morphologies indicating a planktotrophic larval development; however, on the other side, most species do not seem to have broad ranges, which might be congruent with their protoconchs of less than 2 whorls (suggesting relatively short pelagic life and thus, limited dispersal).

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